

GIANTLEAP

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Business case for operators of hydrogen city buses

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Project acronym: GIANTLEAP

Project title: Giantleap Improves Automation of Non-polluting Transportation with Lifetime Extension of Automotive PEM fuel cells

Project number: 700101

Document date: January 31, 2020

Due date: March 31, 2019

Keywords: TCO, Fuel Cell System

Abstract: This document gives an overview about the business case for operators of hydrogen city buses. Cost targets for unit cost of hydrogen buses seem achievable, but even more important is the ability to provide hydrogen at a competitive price.

Revision History

Date	Description	Author
08-28-2019	Draft version 1.0	Harald Fischer
12-19-2019	Draft version 2.0	Harald Fischer
09-01-2020	Final version	Harald Fischer
31-01-2020	Layout adjustments	Federico Zenith (SINTEF)

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1 Scope

This document gives an overview about the business case for operators of hydrogen city buses. The 3 industrial partners ElringKlinger, VDL and Bosch Engineering make an assessment how the respective business ideas, the opportunities of their products, the risks and the timeline and market entry appear.

2 Overview

Bosch Engineering (BEG)

Business idea: The fuel cell system for the trailer can service many different applications and can therefore bundle the volumes, **BEG** offers also development services.

Opportunities: Huge volumes in the bus market can be directly acquired; the concept can be easily transferred to other applications, like mobile machinery, which face similar challenges.

Risks: Prejudice against hydrogen as fuel might lower market acceptance, cost targets might be lower for other applications prohibiting a competitive TCO.

Timeline and Market Entry: Based on positive field test results, Bosch/**BEG** will proof market entry within 3 years after project end. Development services can be offered at any earlier time.

ElringKlinger (EK)

Business idea Stack and stack module based on metallic bipolar plates for bus application and industrial mobility.

Opportunities Market potential of fuel cell stacks and fuel cell system components for urban transport usage is high. Easier market access than in automotive.

Risks H₂ infrastructure not comprehensive yet, and has no unified code and regulations framework. Costs for components (CCM) still high.

Timeline and Market Entry Currently in field-test phase with a material handling application. Starting in the project the bus fuel cell trailer will undergo a field test. Based on results the commercialization steps will be defined to achieve market entry within 3 years. High anode recirculation based on performant ejectors in combination with low pressure drop media compartments enable effective feed gas humidification with simultaneous liquid water discharge to prevent fuel starvation. With regard to the lifetime requirements of the bus application the development and optimization of the anode hydrogen recirculation unit was a major focus for ElringKlinger within the project. That's the reason why ElringKlinger is focused mainly on the development of anode gas recirculation and thus the integration of system functionality directly on the stack module. The direct integration of stack-like anode gas recirculation offers added value to customers and is an important element in further increasing the durability of the stack, which fits well with the project. The work and output of the Giantleap project support the H2Haul project.

VDL

Business idea Public transport will be emission free within 10 years, not all relevant use cases can be covered by opportunity charging.

Opportunities If low Total Cost of Ownership and high reliability can be combined, the Range Extender will see significant demand in the market. The range extender itself is per se cross-platform and independent from the vehicle manufacturer, so VDL can sell it to other OEMs.

Risks High H₂ prices renders achieving low TCO hard; reliability is difficult to achieve in a very challenging operational environment, but key factor for operators: accidents might ruin the technology's image even if not related to hydrogen.

Timeline and Market Entry If the partners agree on a back-to-back guarantee to operators, VDL is willing to commercialize the range extender and makes it usable for trucks, which is an enormous market.

3 Introduction

Based on the industrial partners' market knowledge with respect to regions, applications, products, administrative initiatives and regulatory actions, in this report it will be analysed for multiple target markets the business case for integration of battery buses with hydrogen range extenders equipped with PHM-enhanced control systems, using data for at least three large European cities or metropolitan areas and two extra-European ones, to be chosen such as to represent the widest spectrum of requirements and conditions. The analysis will include a discussion of current or future

standards needed for the successful exploitation of project results within the targeted markets, and how they should be either modified or drafted to maximize the project's impact.

The analysis will produce a report aimed at city bus operators in Europe and worldwide, to present them the business case of hydrogen buses with the application of the methods developed in the project.

A drastic reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is required to keep global warming to below 2 °C, as declared in the 2015 Paris Agreement. Accordingly, the European Union (EU) and its member states are pursuing ambitious GHG reduction targets: Compared to 1990 levels, the EU aims to reduce GHG emissions by 20% by 2020, by 40% by 2030 and by 80 to 95% by 2050. Its member states have defined national targets in line with these goals. Consequently, today's use of fossil fuels across all energy sectors must be drastically reduced. Doing so will in return, decrease dependency on energy imports to the EU and thereby enhance energy security.

To achieve global emission reduction goals, a consistent shift to a green energy system is necessary. The FCH JU's Regions and Cities Initiative supports realisation of the green energy transition in European regions and cities with hydrogen and fuel cells.

As of today, 89 European regions and cities from 22 countries are taking part in the initiative. Together, they represent approximately one quarter of Europe's population, surface area and GDP. All participating regions and cities are actively working to shape their green energy transitions with hydrogen and fuel cells. Regions and cities can play an important role in creating a future FCH market in Europe by channelling public investments into the sector and supporting the build-up of a European FCH value chain with the potential for local economic growth and job creation.

3.1 European Fuel Cell Bus fleets

Figure 1: Overview of participating regions and cities as of May 2018 (Source: Roland Berger, Study for the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking)

3.2 European Bus manufacturers

Table 1: Overview of several bus manufacturers and technical data for 12 m busses (thinkstep, 2018)

Hersteller	Modell	Antriebsart	Entwicklungsstand	Antriebsleistung
SAFRA (FR)	Businova	BZ	Konzept	250 kW (max)
ebeEUROPA (DE)	Blue City Bus (12/18 m)	k. A.	Erprobung	k. A.
EvoBus (DE)	eCitaro mit BZ	BZ-REX	Konzept (die ersten Busse gehen ab 2021 an die Stuttgarter Straßenbahnen)	2x125 kW (max)
Keyou (DE)	k. A.	VM ¹⁴	Konzept	180 kW (Nenn)
Solaris (PL)	Urbino (12/18 m)	BZ und BZ-REX	Konzept (12 m), Erprobung (18 m, Hamburger Hochbahn)	12 m: 2 x 60 kW (Nenn) 18 m: 240 kW (max.)
Wright-bus (UK)	Pulsar Hydrogen	BZ (aktuell nur als Rechtslenker)	Serie	170 kW (max.)
Van Hool (BE)	A330 FC (12 m)/ Exquicity (18 m)	BZ	Serie	210 kW (Nenn)
Toyota (JP) ¹⁵	Sora	BZ	Serienanlauf	2 x 113 kW (max.)
Foton (CN)	BJ6852	BZ	Serienanlauf	k. A.
Yutong (CN)	k. A.	BZ	Serienanlauf	k. A.

3.3 Deployment plans

Table 2: Deployment plans for the FCH applications of participating regions (n=46), (Source: Roland Berger, Study for the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking)

		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Until 2025	Until 2030	2030+	Total
Applications										
Heavy-duty transport applications	Trains		52	2	3	29	189	161	102	538
	Buses	8	109	300	218	244	1.003	1.659	1.665	5.206
	Solo	2	50	65	15		137	280	500	1.049
	Articulated		2			9	50	100	35	196
	Minibuses			1	1		5	8		15
	Not specified	6	57	234	193	244	811	1.271	1.130	3.946
	Heavy-duty trucks	3	17	18	24	8	274	9.110	35.520	44.974
Light- and medium-duty transport applications	Cars	103	327	488	776	780	17.405	191.585	1.023.850	1.235.314
	Vans	49	167	121	263	355	1.565	21.140	20.400	44.060
	Large vans			5		7	20	50	150	232
	Small vans		35	36	100	107	25	60	200	563
	Not specified	49	132	80	163	241	1.520	21.030	20.050	43.265
	Garbage trucks	6	10	60	112	42	144	206	485	1.065
	Sweepers	1	6	10	9	11	2	5	10	54
	Construction mobile equipment/ tools	3	3	3	3	3				15
	Material handling/ forklifts			41	88	110	80	70	50	439
	Bikes	42	35	25	25	11	115	50	75	378
Scooters		5	5		3			100	113	
Maritime applications	Ships/ ferries/ boats	3	5	6	4		8	57	501	584
	Port operations equipment			2				21	32	55
	Yard tractors			1				19	30	50
	Reach stackers			1				2	2	5
Stationary applications	CHP		20	12	1.010	1.007	10.102	50.161		62.312
	Residential use/micro CHPs		1		1.000	1.000	10.000	50.000		62.001
	Commercial CHPs			1	1	1	2	1		6
	Not specified		19	11	9	6	100	160		305

Table 3: Deployment plans for the FCH infrastructure of participating regions (n=46), (Source: Roland Berger, Study for the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking)

	Next Implementation projects					Long-term outlook			Total
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Until 2025	Until 2030	2030+	
Infrastructure									
HRS	27	63	46	73	73	306	319	721	1.628
700 bar	15	26	8	28	12	177	101	500	867
350 bar	4	14	15	18	19	62	74	208	414
combined		6	3	4	10	19	4	4	50
Not specified	8	17	20	23	32	48	140	9	297
Production facilities	10	24	18	23	17	64	31	9	196
Electrolysis	8	15	16	22	13	60	21	8	163
Other			1	1	3		4	1	10
Not specified	2	9	1		1	4	6		23

4 Total Cost of Ownership

The heavy-duty technology pathway is well-established in the market and has achieved significant price reductions since first deployments of FC buses in Europe. FC buses currently in operation in Europe are based on FC bus models designed according to the heavy-duty technology pathway. Since first deployments in the 1990s, purchasing costs for these FC buses have fallen significantly by more than 75%.

Figure 2: FC Bus purchasing cost development since the 1990s (Source: Roland Berger)

Overall costs for these buses are expected to decrease down to a cost premium of about 11-18% compared to conventional diesel buses on a per kilometre basis in the year 2030. The cost premium is driven by the costs associated with the introduction of a new technology, mainly reflected in a higher FC bus purchase price and thus, higher financing costs.

Future costs strongly depend on the size of the market for FC buses. Hence, two scenarios were developed in order to account for potential variations of the future market size as well as the speed at which fuel cell costs will decrease. The "niche scenario" and the "production-at-scale scenario" portray the variance of potential costs depending on efficiencies and economies of scale achieved with varying market sizes and the related overall technological progress in the framework of the heavy-duty technology pathway. The scenarios reflect the effect that different economies of scale have on cost-down curves and prices. For the niche scenario to materialise, a cumulative number of 1,200-1,800 FC buses needs to be deployed on Europe's roads in total until 2025. For the production-at-scale scenario, a total cumulative volume of 8,000-10,000 FC buses is required until 2025.

4.1 TCO Progress

The following chart gives an estimated TCO overview until 2030:

Figure 9: TCO split by components for standard FC buses according to different scenarios in the heavy-duty pathway [EUR/km]

Figure 3: TCO split by components for standard FC buses (Source: Urban buses Brochure)

Underlying are data from different Bus manufacturers and operators. The Department of energy has published similar dates in the past. The following chart gives an overview of the TCO development including the labour costs:

Figure 4: TCO development of FC buses (Source: Fuel cell electric buses FCH JU and Roland Berger)

The breakthrough for fuel cell buses depends significant on the costs of hydrogen. Even a price of 4-5 EUR/kg in the future would be not sufficient for an operating of a fleet of fuel cell buses. The following chart shows a postulated desired cost range:

4.2 Desired Hydrogen cost in the future

Desired H₂ cost range for final design: 4-6 €/kg H₂ (350 bar) @ nozzle

Figure 5: Desired Hydrogen cost (Source: Michael Faltenbacher, thinkstep AG)

Table 4: Energy consumption per 100 km: left column for fuel-cell-only, right column for range extenders (Source: NOW Leitfaden Wasserstoffbusse)

8,5-10,5 kg H ₂	40 – 160 kWh Strom; 0– 6 kg H ₂
	135 kWh Strom; 1 kg H ₂
	80 kWh Strom; 3,5 kg H ₂

Beside the costs of a Hydrogen Bus fleet the following additional costs has to be considered while an operation phase:

- Hydrogen demand
- Number of hydrogen stations in a city, belonging to the calculated throughput
- Investment needs
- Operating costs
- Maintenance
- Costs for workshop customization

4.3 Hydrogen demand

Crucial for the dimensioning of the hydrogen and optionally charging infrastructure, is the daily energy requirement of the fleet to be converted. It depends on various factors. To be able to make an initial estimate of the energy demand, you can focus on the following key aspects:

Vehicle type: Will be a purely hydrogen-powered vehicle or a battery-electric one considered with fuel cell as a range extender?

Vehicle size: The vehicle size is representative of the vehicle weight. Simplifying here only solo and articulated buses (12 m or 18 m vehicles).

Seasons: The different seasons have an influence on the energy consumption of vehicles. Especially in the summer months (cooling) and winter months (heating), this will be higher than in the rest of the year. For the later interpretation of the infrastructure is always use the maximum demand for hydrogen.

Driving profile: This is mainly influenced by stop distances, number of required stops and traffic density, which determine the average speed. For a consumption estimate, the routes can be calculated according to their average speed.

Circulation characteristics and topography: To ascertain the energy demand of the whole fleet, it is important to the specific characteristics of the routes in combination with the driving profile.

Based on the information on number of buses and average route length (upper Table 5) and consumption data (Table 4), we can thus calculate the energy requirements of the entire fleet. As a rule, there are more round trips on working days than on weekends, Sundays and public holidays, and the hydrogen demand is accordingly higher. For the infrastructure design it is therefore necessary to plan for working days in summer.

Table 5: Energy requirements. Calculation based on an average consumption of 9.5 kg H₂/100 km and respectively 80 kWh and 3.5kg H₂/100 km REX.

	BZ	BZ-REX	
Anzahl Solobusse	35	35	
Anzahl Gelenkbusse	15	15	
Mittlere Umlauflänge	250 km	250 km	
	H ₂	H ₂	Strom
Energiebedarf Solobusse (Werte in Klammer: je Bus)	831 kg (24 kg)	306 kg (9 kg)	7 MWh (200 kWh)
Energiebedarf Gelenkbusse (Werte in Klammer: je Bus)	499 kg (33 kg)	263 kg (18 kg)	3 MWh (200 kWh)
Täglicher Gesamtenergiebedarf ⁴	1.330 kg	569 kg	10 MWh

4.4 Costs for the infrastructure

Figure 6: Investment costs depending on fleet size. Left pure FC, right REX (Source: Thinkstep 2018)

4.5 Hydrogen costs

Figure 7: Hydrogen costs in €/kg for in-house production via electrolysis as a function of electricity price (Source: Thinkstep 2018)

For the economics of electrolysis, a favourable electricity price is therefore crucial. Manipulated variables are in addition to the purchase quantity z. B. the reduction of Grid charges by direct connection of the electrolyser to a local power plant (PV, wind farm, waste incineration plant etc.).

In the case of delivery of hydrogen, the running costs consist of Maintenance costs of the plant, logistics costs and hydrogen procurement costs. Figure xx shows this as a function of the hydrogen procurement costs. The running costs represent between 80 and 95 percent of the total costs. Crucial here is the hydrogen reference price, which is based on Experience from completed or ongoing demonstration projects between 3 and 12 euros per kilogram. The big bandwidth is conditioned by the origin of hydrogen. As a by-product of the chemical Industry.

H₂ is often relatively cheap in industry (as a by-product of a chemical reaction e.g. Chlor Alkaly electrolysis). Will it be, for example, by electrolyzers which have relatively low operating hours (e.g. connection to a wind farm at a low-wind location), the H₂ costs are more at the top of the range.

4.6 Hydrogen costs on delivery of the hydrogen

Figure 8: Hydrogen costs in €/kg depending on hydrogen procurement costs (Source: Thinkstep 2018)

4.7 Expected fuel cell bus costs

Figure 9 gives an overview of the expected fuel cell bus costs depending on the volume. The FCH JU target in the H2Bus Europe project (1000 busses) was 375.000 €.

Figure 9: Fuel Cell bus costs (Source: Making Hydrogen and Fuel Cells an everyday reality, Mirela Atanasiu)

Figure 10 shows the expected bus costs in comparison to diesel-hybrid and conventional diesel buses:

Figure 10: Niche scenario and production-at-scale scenario from fuel cell buses compared to Diesel and Diesel Hybrid buses. (Source: FCH-JU, Roland Berger, Fuel Cell Electric Buses)

5 Conclusion

In order to meet the strict targets set by cities and other regulatory bodies, zero-emission powertrains will very likely be a requirement for parts of the fleet in 2020. Hydrogen fuel cell and electric powertrains reduce local emissions to absolute zero, compared to local (tank-to-wheel) emissions of more than 1 kg CO₂/km for a conventional diesel bus. Diesel hybrids (serial and parallel) also offer a reduction of 15 to 20 percent in local emissions, with serial hybrids in particular capable of undertaking longer stretches of the route in full electric drive. Hydrogen fuel cell and other electric powertrains can reduce well-to-wheel GHG emissions by 30 to 100 percent until 2030 compared to Diesel buses. Different powertrains show advantages in different areas of performance. Among the zero local-emission powertrains, the hydrogen fuel cell bus offers the best performance in range, purely electric range and refuelling times, at high operational flexibility. All sources have shown, particularly the TCO calculation of VDL, that the achievement of hydrogen buses will depend highly on the hydrogen price, rather than the cost of the system.

While all alternative powertrains have a more efficient energy conversion and reduce GHG, local and noise emissions significantly, they offer different levels of flexibility and require different amounts of price premium compared to conventional powertrains.

The summary of this calculation is that an economical operation of a Hydrogen fleet is feasible in the future and could compete against combustion engine and battery electric buses. The precondition is, beside low cost for the fuel cell system, a high average availability the price for hydrogen. Taking a hydrogen price of about 3 €/kg as a basis shows that the total operational costs are competitive; the following data are not generally valid but are based on a manufacturer's TCO calculations:

Diesel:

0.89 €/km total

0.40 €/km DSL (45%)

0.00 €/km FC (0%)

0.49 €/km Vehicle (55%)

All incl. maintenance

H₂ now:

2.09 €/km total

0.73 €/km H₂ (35%)

0.67 €/km FC (32%)

0.68 €/km Vehicle (32%). Vehicle is more expensive and second-hand value is 0 €.

All incl. maintenance

H₂ 3 €/kg and < 85.000 €/FC system:

1.20 €/km total

0.22 €/km H₂ (18%)

0.34 €/km FC (28%)

0.64 €/km Vehicle (53%)

All incl. maintenance

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